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Short Report

Predictive Symptomatology in Adult Cases of PANS and PANDAS: A Sentinel for Infection

Progressive manifestations of Pediatric Acute-onset Neuropsychiatric Syndrome (PANS) and Pediatric Autoimmune Neuropsychiatric Disorders Associated with Streptococcal Infections (PANDAS) in adults represent an extension of conditions primarily identified in pediatric populations. Both PANS and PANDAS are typified by the acute emergence or exacerbation of neuropsychiatric symptoms, frequently correlated with an immunological trigger. This case report aims to delineate the clinical features, pathophysiological mechanisms, diagnostic considerations, and therapeutic approaches for these syndromes, extending into adult presentations.^{2,4,5,6,25,26,27}

PANDAS is distinctly associated with Group A streptococcal infections. The diagnostic criteria encompass:

- Emergence of non-psychogenic obsessive-compulsive disorder (OCD) or tic disorders in children and adolescents.
- Episodic, severe exacerbation of symptoms correlating with streptococcal infections.

- Association with neurological abnormalities such as choreiform movements
- Sudden and/or rapid severe exacerbation of symptoms
- Presentation of mild dementia in adults, likely due to chronic-progressive type with ongoing sub-clinical inflammation affecting brain regions such as the substantia nigra and basal ganglia
- Executive function impairment and a broad array of immune-system and CNS anomalies
- Dysfunction of the immune system, either progressive or as lifelong 'scar' of PANDAS
- Cognitive deterioration alongside sensory or motor abnormalities

PANS, a broader categorization, is identified by sudden onset of OCD or extreme dietary restrictions, accompanied by at least two additional neuropsychiatric symptoms not directly linked to a specific infection. These symptoms include:

- Anxiety, emotional instability, and depression
- Irritability, aggression, and oppositional behaviors
- Behavioral regression (or similar symptoms) and executive functioning disturbances
- Cognitive deterioration alongside sensory or motor abnormalities

Pathophysiology

The pathomechanisms involve an immune dysregulation in response to infections that compromise the blood-brain barrier, affecting the central nervous system through mechanisms such as molecular mimicry. This leads to antibody production and autoimmune reactions targeting neuronal tissues, inducing inflammation and directly corresponding neuropsychiatric symptoms.^{6,25,26,27}

Presentation and Management

The diagnosis of PANS and PANDAS is predominantly clinical, supported by the exclusion of other conditions. Therapeutic strategies for adult cases are analogous to pediatric protocols and may include antibiotics for underlying infections, immunomodulation through therapies such as intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) or plasmapheresis, corticosteroids, and targeted treatment for neuropsychiatric symptoms. The recognition and research into these adult manifestations are still evolving, necessitating deeper investigation into their pathophysiology and more refined treatment approaches.

The sentinel case

A 48-year-old male has progressively experienced PANDAS following a severe onset in 1986. Independently of the progression of the syndrome itself, his symptoms intensify when someone nearby becomes infectious, even up to 48 hours before any symptomatic manifestation in him or a household member. This phenomenon, although previously known but seldom discussed, has now been objectively confirmed, underscoring the patient's immune system escalating into an "immune alarm mode," which drives the exacerbation of PANDAS symptoms.

In the spring of 2023, this patient contracted a typical flu, which we seized as an opportunity for observational study. Remarkably, about 48 hours before the onset of infection symptoms, the PANDAS symptoms escalated. The infection manifested with body aches and typical symptoms of a mundane illness. Subsequently, however, the PANDAS symptoms subsided to a "normal level," but the infection transitioned into a runny nose. By the sixth day of the infection, while the escalated PANDAS symptoms had subsided, classic cold symptoms intensified.

The observations suggest that the patient's PANDAS symptoms are triggered by alterations in the immune response, leading to exacerbation upon exposure to infectious agents. The timing of the worsening of

PANDAS symptoms concurrent with the start of an infection supports the hypothesis of autoimmune enhancement through the immunological reaction to infections.

Possible Mechanisms

Cytokine Storm: At the onset of the infection, an increase in pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 or TNF-alpha not only intensifies the infection symptoms but also exacerbates the neuropsychiatric symptoms. These cytokines can compromise the blood-brain barrier, contributing to an amplified neuroinflammatory response.

Molecular Mimicry: The immune response to pathogens may induce cross-reactivity, where antibodies targeting pathogens also attack neural structures, a hallmark of PANDAS.

Regulation of the immune-system: Following the initial immune response surge, a regulatory phase might ensue, characterized by anti-inflammatory mechanisms like IL-10 and TGF-beta production, which mitigate overactivity and aid in normalizing PANDAS symptoms, even in the case that the infection itself persists.^{25,26,27,28}

Conclusion

The landscape of research into adult chronic linear progressive PANS/PANDAS is notably sparse, particularly outside the United States and Asia. Gaining insights from patients who can articulate their experiences thoughtfully may enrich our understanding of the dynamics in younger patients with a typical explosive onset of the disease. This report underscores the necessity of advancing research in this field and suggests that observing the early immunological responses in PANDAS patients could yield crucial insights into the underlying mechanisms of the disease.

Conflicts of interest

None declared.

External funding

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